

LIMNOLOGY AROUND THE WORLD: FRANCE

Thirty years admiring beauty through a microscope

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Bi-Eau is a small firm, specialized in Phycology (www.bieau.fr). The founder, Maria Leitao, was a student of the famous French phycologist Pierre Bourrelly at the Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle, Paris. She created Bi-Eau in 1988, when she moved to a small French town (Angers) where there was no micro-algological research. She started alone, but soon she was joined by young people, creating a small team of 3-4 persons.

Starting without any customers, Bi-Eau has progressively worked with many entities, from water companies, to state environmental agencies to universities. Aiming to keep abreast of the rapidly changing phycological taxonomy and knowledge, the team has participated through the years and all over the world in congresses, workshops and informal meetings, regarding taxonomy as well as ecology. This effort has allowed Bi-Eau to create a scientific network that provides a high level of expertise in algology, and acts as a scientific guarantee of its work (Fig 1). Through the years, Bi-Eau has also hosted many students from universities across Europe doing their thesis work regarding algae. Our studies mainly concern France and French territories, but sometimes we also work on other freshwaters (Belgium, England, Italy, Spain...). More than analysing samples, Bi-Eau also tries to offer additional considerations about the limnological situation of the studied site, therefore optimizing its analytical work with the added value of ecological interpretations.

In some particular cases, new situations or interesting phenomenon arise that warrant publishing the results (with customer agreement), and to share these experiences with other limnologists and readers of scientific journals such as *Hydrobiologia*, *Journal of Plankton Research*, *Freshwater Biology*, *Ecological Indicators*, *Phycological Studies*, *PloSone*... For example, Bi-Eau was the first to document the presence of the cyanobacterium *Cylindrospermopsis* in France. Thanks to this work, always done in collaboration

Fig. 1 Preparing a phytoplankton sample.

with international experts, the staff of Bi-Eau constantly improve their general knowledge (and make a lot of good friends!).

In a world that is progressively using more genetic tools and biochemical methods, Bi-Eau still believes that recognizing a whole organism or observing a natural population through a microscope, remains an ecological advantage and a personal privilege. Therefore, for more than 30 years, Bi-Eau has worked seriously, with passion, hoping that these small/micro observations, will lead to a better understanding of the world.

Fig. 2 Some photographs: a) *Anabaenopsis elenkenii*; clockwise *Durinskia balticum*, Christmas cookies, *Epithemia adnata*, *Stephanodiscus*.

Publications

Minaudo C, Abonyi A, Leitao M, Floury M, Descy JP, Moatar F. 2021. Long-term of nutrient control, climate change and invasive clams on phytoplankton and cyanobacteria biomass in a large temperate river. *Science of Total Environment* <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.144074>

Rugema E, Darchambeau F, Sarmiento H, Stoyneva-Gartner M, Leitao M, Thiery W, Latli A, Descy JP. 2019. Long-term change of phytoplankton in Lake Kivu: the rise of the greens. *Freshwater Biology* 1-16.

Yvon-Durocher G, Allen AP, Cellamare M, Dossena M, Gaston KJ, Leitao M, Montoya JM, Reuman DC, Woodward G, Trimmer M. 2015. Five years of experimental warming increases the biodiversity and productivity of phytoplankton. *PLoS Biol* 13: e1002324.

Cellamare M, Lançon AM, Leitao M, Cerasino L, Oberegger U, Flaim G. 2015. Phytoplankton functional responses to spatial and temporal differences in a cold and oligotrophic lake. *Hydrobiologia* 764: 199–209.

Abonyi A, Leitao M, Stankovic I, Borics G, Varbiro G, Padišak J. 2014. A large river (River Loire, France) survey to compare phytoplankton functional approaches: do they display river zones in similar ways? *Ecological Indicators* 46: 11–22.

Cellamare M, Tezanos-Pinto P, Leitao M, Coste M, Boutry S, Haury J. 2013. Using functional approaches to study phytoplankton communities in a temperate region exposed to tropical species dispersal. *Hydrobiologia* 702: 267–282.

Descy JP, Leitao M, Everbecq E, Smitz JS, Delière JF. 2012. Phytoplankton of the River Loire, France: a biodiversity and modelling study. *Journal of Plankton Research* 34: 120-135.

Abonyi A, Leitao M, Lançon AM, Padišak J. 2012. Phytoplankton functional groups as indicators of human impacts along the River Loire (France). *Hydrobiologia* 698: 233-249.

Stoyneva M, Descy JP, Balague V, Compere P, Leitao M, Sarmiento H. 2012. The queer *Tetraëdron minimum* from Lake Kivu (Eastern Africa): is it a result of a human impact? *Hydrobiologia* 698:273-283.

Cellamare M, Leitao M, Haury J, Dutarte A. 2010. Tropical phytoplankton taxa in Aquitaine Lakes (France). *Hydrobiologia* 63: 129-145.

Oudin LC, Lair N, Leitao M, & al. 2009. The Loire Basin. in: *Rivers of Europe*, Chap. 5.2, Ed. Tockner & al., Elsevier, 700 pp.

Sarmiento H, Leitao M, Stoyneva M, Compere P, Couté A, Descy JP. 2007. Diversity of pelagic algae of Lake Kivu (East Africa). *Algologie-Cryptogamie* 28: 245-269.

AFSSA – AFSSET Working Group. 2006. Évaluation des risques liés à la présence de cyanobactéries et de leurs toxines dans les eaux destinées à l'alimentation, à la baignade et aux activités récréatives. 270 pp. <https://www.anses.fr/fr/system/files/EAUX-Ra-Cyanobacteries.pdf>

Leitao M, Couté A. 2005. Guide des Cyanobactéries planctoniques du Grand Ouest de la France : à l'usage des gestionnaires des eaux de surface. 60 pp.

Couté A, Leitao M, Sarmiento H. 2004. Une nouvelle espèce d'algue d'eau douce (Cyanophyceae), trouvée en France. *Algological Studies* 111: 1-15.

Leitao M, Morata SM, Rodriguez S, Vergon JP. 2003. The effect of perturbations on phytoplankton assemblages in a deep reservoir (Vouglans, France). *Hydrobiologia* 502: 73-83.

Leitao M, & al., 2001. *Peridiniopsis corillionii* sp. nova (Dinophyta), une nouvelle espèce Dinophycée d'eau douce de France responsable de marée rouge en rivière. *Algological Studies* 102: 1-15.

Leitao M, Leglize L. 2000. Long-term variations of epilimnic phytoplankton in an artificial reservoir during a ten-year survey. *Hydrobiologia* 424: 39-49.

Leitao M, Couté A. 1999. Cas d'une marée rouge en rivière provoquée par un *Peridiniopsis* (Dinophyceae). *Journal Botanique de France* 12: 87-89.

Kelly MG, et al. 1998. Recommendations for routine sampling of diatoms for water quality assessments in Europe. *J. of Applied Phycology*, 10: 215-224.

Leitao M, Lepretre A. 1998. The phytoplankton of the river Loire: a typological approach. *Verh. Internat. Verein. Limnol.*, 26: 1050-1056.

Couté A, Leitao M, Martin C. 1997. Première observation du genre *Cylindrospermopsis* en France (Cyanophyceae, Nostocales). *Algologie-Cryptogamie* 18: 57-70.

Leitao M, 1995. Eutrophisation du Loir et son incidence sur l'usine d'eau potable de La Flèche (Sarthe). *TSM* 1: 31-37.

Przygiel J, Leitao M. 1994. Cyanophycean blooms in the reservoir of Val Joly (northern France) and their development in downstream rivers. *Hydrobiologia* 289: 85-96.

Leitao M, 1985. Evolution algale dans un bassin de rétention d'eau à Orly. *Rev. Française des Sciences de l'Eau* 4: 45-53.

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